

MORPHOLOGY OF THE CHOROID PLEXUS OF THE BRAIN OF RATS UNDER VARIOUS METHODS OF EUTHANASIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13309034>

Annotation. The comparative morphology of the choroid plexus of the ventricles of the brain of rats was studied during euthanasia with an overdose of anesthesia and during euthanasia by acute experimental blood loss by transection of the carotid artery and abdominal aorta. It has been established that during euthanasia by an overdose of anesthesia, the plexus vessels are located compactly, and during euthanasia by blood loss they diverge. These phenomena during transection of the carotid artery are more obvious in comparison with those with transection of the abdominal aorta.

Key words: choroid plexus of cerebral ventricles, comparative morphology in experiment

Relevance. The soft consistency of the brain substance and its location in a limited space inside the skull requires reliable protection from mechanical influences. Therefore, nature has created a liquid hydration and shock-absorbing system around it, represented by cerebrospinal fluid, which is produced by the choroid plexus of the ventricles of the brain. This fluid fills the subarachnoid space of the brain and spinal cord, the ventricles of the brain and the central canal of the spinal cord. The production, renewal, and therefore circulation of this fluid is directly related to the blood. Therefore, changes in blood supply and pressure in the vascular system of the brain are reflected in the pressure and volume of this fluid in the cavities of the ventricles of the brain. Scientific works devoted to the study of the choroid plexus of humans [1,4] and laboratory animals [2,3] are available. Often in morphological experimental studies, euthanasia (killing) of laboratory animals by bloodletting is used. Naturally, this also leads to bleeding of the brain vessels, and therefore the choroid plexus of its ventricles. But with euthanasia by overdose of anesthesia, this does not happen. The issue of comparative study of the morphology of the choroid plexus in one or another method of euthanasia is one of the insufficiently studied. From this point of view, studying the morphology of the choroid plexus of the ventricles of the brain, which is a producer of

cerebrospinal fluid, in various methods of euthanasia is one of the pressing issues.

Objective of the work: To study the morphology of the choroid plexuses of the ventricles of the brain of rats during euthanasia by bloodletting and anesthesia overdose

Material and research methods. The choroid plexus of the ventricles of the brain was studied in 16 rats: 8 rats after euthanasia from acute experimental blood loss (by transection of the carotid artery in 4 rats, and by transection of the abdominal aorta in 4 rats), 8 rats after euthanasia by an overdose of anesthesia. Euthanasia of rats was carried out in compliance with all bioethical requirements and under anesthesia. The brain is fixed in 12% neutral formalin and completely embedded in paraffin. Histological processing of the material was carried out according to generally accepted methods. Relatively thick histotopographic sections of the brain were stained with hematoxylin–eosin and Nissl thionin.

Research results. In rats that were euthanized by an overdose of anesthesia, the choroid plexus of the ventricles of the brain is represented by densely packed vessels (Fig. 1A). The free space between the plexus vessels is insignificant and is visible in the form of a light layer of various configurations

Fig.1. Choroid plexus of the ventricle of the rat brain, during euthanasia by anesthesia overdose (A) and acute blood loss (B) due to transection of the abdominal aorta. Staining using hematoxylin-eosin method. About. 20, approx. 7.

As can be seen from the figure, the plexus vessels having almost the same caliber are located close to each other and the main vessel, apparently supplying blood to the plexus vessels, is quite large. caliber. And this vessel is also full-blooded. During euthanasia of acute blood loss, the choroid plexus has the appearance of a branchy tree (Fig. 1B). The vessels move away from each other and the space between them expands. In this case, you can notice. that from the main vessel

begins the anchor blood vessel, which branches out to form a plexus and they are all connected to each other and to the branches of the anchor vessel. We observed a similar picture when comparing choroid plexus preparations during transection of the carotid artery during euthanasia of anesthesia overdose. Moreover, during euthanasia by an overdose of anesthesia, the location of the plexus vessels is also more compact (Fig. 2A), and during euthanasia by blood loss, the vessels diverge (Fig. 2B). It should be noted that with euthanasia with transection of the carotid artery, the picture of vascular divergence is more demonstrative. And in this case, the main blood vessel and the anchor blood vessel branching off from it forming the choroid plexus are also visible.

Fig.2. Choroid plexus of the 4th ventricle of the rat brain during euthanasia by an overdose of anesthesia (A) and during euthanasia by acute blood loss by transection of the carotid artery. Nissl thionin staining. Vol.20, 0k 7.

Thus, in rats euthanized by bloodletting, the blood vessels of the ventricular plexus fan out. Free space appears between the plexus vessels. And the anchor blood vessel, due to the branching that forms the choroid plexus of the ventricles, is directly connected to the collector blood vessel. During euthanasia with an overdose of anesthesia, the plexus vessels are located compactly around the collector blood vessel.

Conclusions: The results of our research suggest that there is a balance of volume and pressure between the circulatory and liquor systems of the brain. During euthanasia by an overdose of anesthesia, the plexus vessels are located more compactly, and during euthanasia by bloodletting they diverge. Apparently, acute blood loss leads to bleeding of the vessels of the plexus of the ventricles of the brain and they seem to “float up” in their cavity containing cerebrospinal fluid. These data can serve as additional help in assessing the

results of experimental studies on the morphology of cerebrospinal fluid producers.

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